

Different effects of tocopherol natural extract on sunflower oil stability under frying and accelerated storage conditions: A comprehensive study on the fate of major and minor components of oil, and added tocopherols

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1 **Abstract**

2 The effect of adding a tocopherol-rich natural extract (TNE) at 0.1% and 0.5% on
3 sunflower oil stability under frying and accelerated storage conditions was studied using
4 ¹H NMR and DI-SPME-GC/MS. The impact was more pronounced at the higher
5 enrichment level under both conditions. During frying conditions, oil stability
6 significantly decreased due to accelerated degradation of linoleate and minor
7 components (tocopherols, squalene and sterols), along with a marked increase in oil
8 viscosity. Additionally, the selective generation of aldehydes occurred, with the
9 formation of alkanals, *E*-2-alkenals and toxic oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes
10 being lagged. Under storage, TNE initially promoted linoleate degradation and the
11 formation of monohydroperoxy-odacedadienoates but delayed their transformation into
12 secondary or further compounds. Similarly, the degradation of oil minor components
13 occurred more slowly. Tocopherol-derived metabolites varied depending on processing
14 conditions. Pristane was the most abundant during frying, while 4,8,12,16-
15 tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide predominated under storage conditions. Formyl
16 derivatives were identified for the first time.

17

18 **Keywords:** tocopherol natural extract; sunflower oil; frying and accelerate storage
19 conditions; thermo-degradation; polymerisation; major and minor compounds;
20 tocopherol oxidation metabolites.

21

22 1. INTRODUCTION

23 The technological performance of edible oils and fats primarily depends on their lipid
24 composition (both major and minor components) and processing conditions (e.g.,
25 temperature, oxygen availability, light exposure), as these factors determine the rate and
26 mechanisms of lipid degradation (Goicoechea & Guillén, 2010; Guillén & Uriarte,
27 2012a,b). Despite its high degree of polyunsaturation, which makes it prone to
28 degradation, sunflower oil is used for food processing worldwide. In an effort to extend
29 shelf life, the food industry has enriched oils with compounds possessing potential
30 antioxidant capacity (CPAC) for decades. This strategy aims to delay the loss of
31 nutritional and sensorial quality and ensure product safety (Frankel, 2005; 2007). The
32 current trend focuses on identifying natural antioxidants, particularly from agri-food by-
33 products (López-Pedrouso et al., 2022), as alternatives to synthetic and semi-synthetic
34 compounds such as 2,6-di-tert-butyl-hydroxytoluene and tert-butyl-hydroquinone.
35 Although widely used, these compounds have raised health concerns among consumers
36 regarding their safety and healthfulness (Nieva-Echevarría et al., 2015).

37 Among natural CPACs, tocopherols stand out as minor lipid soluble—molecules
38 commonly present in vegetable oils (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2017). Many studies have
39 investigated the effectiveness of individual tocopherols in enhancing lipid stability
40 across various food model systems, vegetable oils, emulsions and/or purified oil
41 triglycerides under different thermo-oxidative conditions (Mäkinen et al., 2000;
42 Mäkinen et al., 2001; Warner & Moser, 2009; Márquez-Ruiz et al., 2014; Martínez-
43 Yusta & Guillén, 2019; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022a,b). Although valuable, the available
44 information remains inconsistent. Discrepancies persist, with studies reporting no effect,
45 pro-oxidant effects, or antioxidant effects for the same compound under similar
46 oxidative conditions. Comparisons are challenging due to variations in lipidic models,

47 CPAC concentrations, oxidative conditions, and analytical techniques employed. These
48 methodologies, often ‘classical’ approaches, may lack specificity and provide limited
49 insights into oxidation processes, as they typically measure only a few markers on
50 which conclusions are based.

51 Moreover, beyond their natural origin, the food industry requires CPACs to be as
52 effective as possible under a wide range of processing conditions. Since using CPACs in
53 mixtures may better delay lipid degradation compared to individual compounds,
54 (Bayran & Decker, 2023), recent interest has focused on natural plant extracts (Grandois
55 et al., 2017; Mishra et al., 2021; Erickson et al., 2023; Abdo et al., 2023), particularly
56 those containing mixtures of various tocopherol isoforms. Although abundant data
57 exists on the effectiveness of individual tocopherols in enhancing oil stability under
58 different oxidative conditions, fewer studies address the performance of mixed
59 tocopherols, and even fewer focus on tocopherol-rich natural extracts (Huang et al.
60 1995; Wagner & Elmadfa, 2000; Nogala-Kalucka et al., 2005; Tabee et al., 2008;
61 Aladedunye & Przybylski, 2012; Grandois et al., 2017; Galanakis et al., 2018;
62 Athanasiadis et al., 2023). Furthermore, the results remain inconclusive.

63 For this reason, the primary objective of the present study was to evaluate the
64 performance of a tocopherol natural extract, derived from sunflower oil by-products, in
65 enhancing the stability of sunflower oil under various degradative conditions, including
66 frying and accelerated storage. To achieve this, Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
67 (^1H NMR) spectroscopy and Direct Immersion-Solid Phase Microextraction-Gas
68 Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (DI-SPME-GC/MS) were employed to study the
69 fate of both polyunsaturated acyl groups and minor compounds of nutritional interest,
70 such as squalene, sterols and tocopherol isoforms (both naturally present and added).
71 These techniques have proven highly effective for monitoring the evolution of lipidic

72 components, and identifying metabolites derived from their degradation. To date,
73 studies providing a comprehensive view of the various oxidation products formed in
74 edible oils enriched with tocopherol natural mixtures are lacking. To the best of our
75 knowledge, kinetic studies on the evolution of several minor components in the
76 presence of added tocopherols have not yet been conducted.

77 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

78 **2.1. Oil samples and tocopherol natural extract under study**

79 Refined sunflower oil from the same batch and brand was purchased from a local
80 supplier. According to the label, the content of total tocopherols was 78 mg/100 g (i.e.
81 0.078% w/w) and the oil contained no added synthetic antioxidants. Aliquots of refined
82 sunflower oil (**SF0**) were enriched in the laboratory with a commercial tocopherol
83 natural extract (TNE) at two concentrations: 0.1% by weight for **SF01** and 0.5% for
84 **SF05**. TNE was purchased from a food additives supplier and derived from the
85 distillation of sunflower oil extracted from non-genetically modified seeds. The extract
86 had a total tocopherol concentration of 50.1%, with the following relative proportions of
87 tocopherol isoforms: α (65.1%), $\gamma+\beta$ (21.2%), and δ (13.7%).

88 The oil and TNE were mixed and stirred for ten minutes at room temperature. To
89 minimise the risk of photo-oxidation of both sunflower oil and TNE, exposure to light
90 was kept to a minimum during sample preparation. The concentrations employed were
91 selected to cover a range of potentially useful levels, as recommended by the supplier.

92 **2.2. Thermal treatment experiments**

93 **2.2.1. Frying conditions experiments at 170 °C in the absence of food**

94 Under severe heating conditions, 3 litres of each oil type (SF0, SF01 and SF05) were
95 separately placed into F-3 Sammic professional fryers (Azpeitia, Spain) with a stainless-
96 steel tank measuring 180 mm wide x 360 mm long x 420 mm high. The oil samples
97 were heated in the absence of food at 170 ± 5 °C for a 6-hour cycle per day until the
98 total polar compounds (TPC) reached 25% (after six days), which is the legal threshold
99 for frying oil reuse in many countries (Hwang et al., 2020). It should be noted that the
100 initial TPC percentage of SF0, SF01 and SF05 was 7%. Since the professional fryers
101 lacked probes, oil temperature was continuously monitored using a Testo 175-T3
102 temperature logger (Testo SE & Co. KGaA, Leizkirch, Germany). The TPC percentage
103 was determined hourly using a Testo 270 instrument (Testo SE & Co. KGaA), with an
104 accuracy of $\pm 3.0\%$ TPC. The data from this instrument are based on the dielectric
105 constant of the oil, which is directly proportional to the weight percentage of polar
106 compounds present. Oil samples (6 mL) were collected every 6-12 hours during heating
107 for up to 138 hours and stored at -80 °C until further analysis. These samples were
108 labelled as **SF0_170** (non-enriched sunflower oil), **SF01_170** (sunflower oil enriched at
109 0.1%) and **SF05_170** (sunflower oil enriched at 0.5%). Throughout the heating period,
110 the oil was not replenished. As a result of the samplings, nearly 140 mL of the total
111 heated oil volume was removed from each fryer by the end of the experiment. To ensure
112 consistency, these heating experiments were conducted in duplicate.

113 **2.2.2. Accelerated storage condition experiments (70 °C)**

114 Non-enriched and enriched oils were also subjected to less severe heating conditions,
115 typical of accelerated storage experiments. For this purpose, ten grams of each oil type
116 were weighed into crystal Petri dishes (80 mm diameter) and placed in a convection
117 oven (Mettler GmbH+Co, Schwabach, Germany) at $70 \text{ °C} \pm 5 \text{ °C}$ with circulating air
118 until total polymerisation was reached (10 days for non-enriched oil and 13 days for

119 enriched). Total polymerisation was defined as the point at which the oil viscosity
120 increased to the extent that it no longer flowed when poured, effectively becoming
121 solid. To ensure consistency, these heating experiments were conducted in duplicate.
122 Samples were taken every 24 hours during the heating period to monitor lipid
123 degradation. The samples subjected to these conditions were labelled as **SF0_70** (non-
124 enriched sunflower oil), **SF01_70** (sunflower oil enriched at 0.1%) and **SF05_70**
125 (sunflower oil enriched at 0.5%). As previously mentioned, samples were stored at -80
126 °C for up to two weeks prior to analysis.

127 **2.3. ¹H NMR study of linoleic acyl group degradation and oxidation product** 128 **formation in non-enriched and enriched oils under frying and accelerated storage** 129 **conditions**

130 **2.3.1. ¹H NMR spectra acquisition**

131 The ¹H NMR spectra of the oil samples were acquired in duplicate using a Bruker
132 Avance 400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz (Bruker Scientific Instruments,
133 Billerica, USA). Sample preparation, acquisition conditions and spectral data analysis
134 followed the protocols used in previous studies (Guillén & Ruiz, 2003, 2004;
135 Goicoechea & Guillén, 2010). In brief, 175 µl of oil were mixed in a 5 mm diameter
136 tube with 425 µl of deuterated chloroform (CDCl₃) (Euroisotop, Paris, France),
137 containing 0.2% non-deuterated chloroform and 0.03% tetramethylsilane (TMS), which
138 served as the reference compound for chemical shift calibration at 0.0 ppm. To optimise
139 acquisition parameters for accurate and efficient quantitative results, a wide range of
140 recycling times and relaxation delays were tested. The selected parameters were:
141 spectral width of 6410 Hz, relaxation delay of 3 s, four dummy scans, 64 scans, an
142 acquisition time of 2.621 s, pulse width of 90° and a total acquisition time of 6 min 20 s.

143 These parameters ensured complete relaxation of the proton nuclei, making the signal
144 areas proportional to the number of protons generating them.

145 The spectra shown in **Figures 1** and **6** were plotted at a fixed value of absolute intensity
146 to be valid for comparative purposes using MNova program (Mestrelab Research,
147 Santiago de Compostela, Spain). The identification of the several major and minor
148 compounds, including oxidation products, in the samples was based on standard
149 compounds and data reported in the literature (Guillén & Ruiz, 2003; Alberdi-Cedeño et
150 al., 2020). Assignment of the chemical shifts and multiplicities of the ^1H NMR signals
151 in deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3) is provided in supplementary **Table S1**.

152 **2.3.2. Quantification from ^1H NMR spectral data**

153 Since the area of each spectral signal is proportional to the number of protons
154 generating it, and the proportionality constant in the ^1H NMR spectrum is the same for
155 all protons types, several quantitative determinations were performed using spectral
156 data. In each oil sample, the molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups (AG)—the main
157 lipid component in sunflower oil— was quantified, along with the molar concentration
158 (expressed as mmol/mol AG) of various oxidation compounds, including isomers of
159 conjugated dienic systems supported in octadecadienoates with hydroperoxy or keto
160 groups, and different types of aldehydes. The equations employed for these
161 determinations are those used in previous studies (Guillén & Uriarte, 2012a,b; Alberdi-
162 Cedeño et al., 2020).

163 **2.4. Study of the fate of minor components of interest in oil samples using DI- 164 SPME-GC/MS: tocopherols, sterols and squalene, whether added or naturally 165 present**

166 The evolution of several minor oil components was analysed using Direct Immersion-
167 Solid Phase Microextraction followed by Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (DI-
168 SPME-GC/MS), applying the same methodology and operating conditions as in a
169 previous study (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2017). Identification of various sterols, squalene,
170 tocopherol isoforms and their degradation products was primarily achieved with
171 commercial standards acquired from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), marked with an
172 asterisk in **Tables 1** and **2**. When standards were not available, mass spectra matching
173 with data from previous studies (Nagata et al., 1999; Al-Malaika et al., 2001; Alberdi-
174 Cedeño et al., 2019) served as identification criterion.

175 Semi-quantification of selected components was based on the area counts of the base
176 peak (Bp) of each compound's mass spectrum. While chromatographic response factors
177 differ among compounds, these area counts enable comparison of compound abundance
178 across different samples.

179 **2.5. Assessment of viscosity in oil**

180 The viscosity of the three types of oils heated at frying temperatures was monitored
181 after each 6-hour heating cycle using a Visco Star + L rotational viscometer
182 (FungilabTM, Barcelona, Spain). As indicated by the manufacturer's instructions, 500 ml
183 of oil at 25 °C was placed in a 600 ml beaker, and the spindle was immersed in the oil at
184 200 rpm, until a stable reading was achieved.

185 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

186 Microsoft Office Excel 2016 was used for the graphical representation of several
187 quantitative determinations (**Figures 2-5** and **7-8**), and for generating the equations
188 corresponding to the lines of best fit presented in **Tables 1** and **2**. Statistical significance
189 among the different determinations for heated oils was assessed using one-way analysis

190 of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's b test at $p < 0.05$, performed with SPSS
191 Statistics v.28 software (IBM, NY, USA). Graphically represented values correspond to
192 averages, and error bars were omitted because they are too small to be visually
193 discernible. These are given in the Supplementary Material (**Tables S2-7 and S9-12**).

194

195 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

196 **3.1. Effect of tocopherol natural extract (TNE) on sunflower oil stability during** 197 **frying conditions (170 °C) in the absence of food**

198 For the three types of oil under study, the experiment was concluded after 138 hours of
199 heating, as this time point corresponded to the attainment of 25% total polar compounds
200 (TPC). The curves representing the evolution of TPC percentage overlapped completely
201 (data not shown), indicating no significant impact of TNE enrichment on sunflower oil
202 stability. Notably, 25% TPC is the regulatory threshold for frying oil reuse in many
203 countries. However, this parameter lacks specificity and does not provide information
204 on the nature of the compounds formed during oil thermo-degradation or the
205 degradation of oil components. Therefore, it would be necessary to assess a broader
206 range of markers of oil thermo-degradation to identify potential differences between
207 non-enriched and TNE-enriched oils, if any, and to better understand the effect of TNE
208 on sunflower oil stability at frying temperatures.

209 **3.1.1 Differences in the degradation of linoleic acyl groups degradation**

210 Previous studies on changes in oil composition during heating at frying temperatures
211 have shown that the acyl group with the highest degradation rate is typically the
212 predominant one, regardless of its degree of unsaturation (Guillén & Uriarte 2012a,b;
213 Martínez-Yusta & Guillén, 2014, 2016). In the case of sunflower oil, this is linoleic

214 (C18:2 ω -6). **Figure 2a** illustrates the evolution of the molar percentage of this acyl
215 group in sunflower oil, both enriched (SF01_170 and SF05_170) and non-enriched
216 (SF0_170), when heated at 170 °C until 25% TPC was reached. As expected, linoleic
217 acyl groups gradually decreased in all samples as heating progressed (see signal **a** in
218 **Figure 1**). For all oil samples, data fitted a linear zero-order equation in agreement with
219 previous studies (Guillén & Uriarte 2012a; Martínez-Yusta & Guillén, 2016). No
220 significant differences in the evolution of linoleic acyl groups were observed between
221 SF0_170 and SF01_170, with the degradation rates of linoleic acyl groups being nearly
222 identical in the absence ($-0.0737\% \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$) and presence of the extract at 0.1% ($-$
223 $0.0755\% \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$). However, at the highest enrichment level (0.5%), a significantly
224 higher degradation rate was observed ($-0.0821\% \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$), becoming evident from the
225 24th hour of heating onwards (see SF05_170 curve in Figure 1a). These results suggest
226 that the addition of the assayed TNE does not improve frying oil stability, and may
227 actually decrease it when added at 0.5%. In addition to reducing the technological
228 properties and nutritional value of the frying oil, the enrichment with TNE could also
229 impair its safety, as higher concentrations of thermo-degradation products are likely to
230 form.

231 **3.1.2 Differences in the generation of oxidation products detected by ¹H NMR**

232 As a result of unsaturated acyl group degradation, several oxidation products were
233 formed in sunflower oil heated at frying temperatures, and these were identified by ¹H
234 NMR. No proton signals related to primary oxidation compounds (monohydroperoxy-
235 conjugated octadecadienoates) were detected in the spectra of heated samples (see
236 signal **c** in **Figure 1**), in accordance with previous studies on vegetable oil thermo-
237 oxidation at high temperatures (Guillén & Uriarte, 2012a; Martínez-Yusta & Guillén,

238 2016). This absence can be attributed to the low oxygen availability and the high
239 instability of these compounds at frying temperatures, should they be formed. Instead,
240 spectral signals corresponding to the protons of monoketo-conjugated
241 octadecadienoates in *E,E* configuration, as well as several types of aldehydes were
242 detected (see signals **d-n** in **Figure 1**). The evolution of their concentrations is shown in
243 **Figures 3a-h**.

244 The evolution of *E,E*-monoketo-octadecadienoates followed a similar trend in
245 SF0_170, SF01_170 and SF05_170 (see **Figure 3a**). These oxidation products can be
246 considered secondary, as they are formed from the decomposition of hydroperoxy-
247 octadecadienoates, particularly after homolytic cleavage into hydroxyl and alkoxy
248 radicals (Brühl, 2014). Previous studies have shown that epoxy, hydroxy, and keto are
249 the main functional groups identified in the acyl chains attached to the triglyceride
250 molecule in used frying oils (Márquez-Ruiz & Dobarganes, 2007). However, in
251 sunflower oil heated at 180 °C, the level of keto-containing compounds was the lowest
252 among these three functional groups (Marmesat, Velasco & Dobarganes, 2008a). In
253 contrast, proton signals corresponding to monohydroxy-octadecadienoates and epoxy
254 groups in fatty acyl chains were not observed in this study (Alberdi-Cedeño et al.,
255 2020).

256 Regarding **aldehydes**, both non-enriched and enriched oils exhibited a similar profile,
257 although some differences were noticeable. Aldehydes of the same nature were
258 generated in all three types of oils (see **Figure 1**), with *E,E*-2,4-alkadienals (signal **f₂**),
259 *E*-2-alkenals (signal **g**), and alkanals (signal **l**), being detected at the highest
260 concentrations, followed by *E,Z*-2,4-alkadienals (signal **k**) and the oxygenated
261 aldehydes: 4-oxo-alkanals, 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-alkenals and 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals (signals
262 **n**, **i** and **h**, respectively). As shown in **Figures 3b-h**, overall, when 25% TPC was

263 reached, all these aldehydes exhibited their maximum concentrations, although the
264 values were relatively low, especially for the oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes
265 (approximately 0.1 and 0.2 mmol/mol AG for 4,5-epoxy- and 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-alkenals,
266 respectively).

267 Regarding potential differences in the generation of these secondary oxidation products
268 among the samples, different trends were observed depending on the nature of the
269 aldehyde. For instance, as shown in **Figures 3c** and **3d**, the generation rate of *E*-2-
270 alkenals and alkanals was higher in non-enriched compared to enriched oils.
271 Specifically, for *E*-2-alkenals, the generation rate was 0.0081 mmol/mol AG * hour⁻¹ in
272 SF0_170, versus 0.0072 and 0.0060 mmol/mol AG * hour⁻¹ in SF01_170 and
273 SF05_170, respectively; for alkanals, the rates were 0.0062 mmol/mol AG * hour⁻¹ in
274 SF0_170, compared to 0.0050 and 0.0045 mmol/ mol AG * hour⁻¹ in SF01_170 and
275 SF05_170, respectively. Conversely, no clear differences in the evolution of *E,E*- and
276 *E,Z*-2,4-alkadienals were observed between SF0_170 and SF05_170 (see **Figures 3b**
277 **and 3e**). Furthermore, enrichment with TNE at the highest level caused a 6-hour delay
278 in the generation of both 4-hydroxy- and 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals (from hour 0 to hour 6
279 and from hour 12 to hour 18, respectively) (see **Figures 3g and 3h**). Contrarily, it
280 accelerated the generation of 4-oxo-alkanals, which occurred 24 hours earlier (from
281 hour 48 to hour 24) (see **Figure 3f**). An intermediate effect was observed at the lower
282 enrichment level. This result may be of interest, considering the high reactivity of
283 oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, which have been associated with several
284 diseases, including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's and cancer (Guillén & Goicoechea, 2008).
285 However, it should be noted that at the enrichment levels employed, very slight
286 differences in the molar concentrations of these aldehydes were observed between non-
287 enriched and enriched oils (up to \approx 0.05 mmol/mol AG).

288 It seems that the presence of TNE leads to a selective generation of aldehydes,
289 favouring certain pathways while disfavouring others. Specifically, it seems to reduce
290 the formation of oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, alkanals and *E*-2-alkenals,
291 while promoting the generation of 4-oxo-alkanals. Previous studies on the effect of
292 tocopherol addition (either as single isoforms or mixtures) on secondary oxidation
293 product formation at frying temperatures have mostly determined the unspecific marker,
294 Anisidine Value (Nogala-Kalucka et al., 2005; Tabee et al., 2008; Galanakis et al.,
295 2018), and such selective effect has not been reported before. To our knowledge, only
296 one prior study (Aladedunye & Przybylski, 2012) has analysed a range of specific
297 aldehydes by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). In that study, 4-
298 hydroxy-*E*-2-nonenal and various volatile carbonyls from the alkanal, *E*-2-alkenal, and
299 2,4-alkadienal families were identified. Significantly lower concentrations of all these
300 aldehydes were detected in stripped canola oil enriched with different tocopherol
301 mixtures (up to 0.2% w/w) irrespective of the isoform proportions in the mixture and
302 the enrichment level tested.

303 **3.1.3. Differences in oil viscosity**

304 Among the several products generated during oil thermo-degradation, triglyceride
305 polymers have been highlighted as a significant component. It has been reported that
306 polymerisation reactions occur at a much faster rate than oxidative ones at frying
307 temperatures (Gertz et al., 2014), and these can begin in the early stages of heating
308 through C–C bonds formed between unsaturated acyl group chains (Márquez-Ruiz et
309 al., 2014). Other authors have also indicated the substantial role of ether (Patrikios &
310 Mavromoustakos, 2014) and ester bonds in the cross-linking of acyl chains (Bonetti &
311 Parker, 2019; Hwang et al., 2020). Viscosity is a widely accepted indicator of heated oil
312 quality, as this physical property has been shown to correlate positively with polymer

313 formation (Kress-Rogers et al., 1990; Hwang et al., 2020). Therefore, to indirectly
314 monitor the progression of polymerisation reactions, changes in oil viscosity were
315 tracked throughout the entire experiment under frying conditions (see **Figure 4**).

316 As expected, the viscosity of all oil samples gradually increased as the experiment
317 progressed. Regarding potential differences between control and enriched oils, similar
318 changes were observed in all three oil types up until the 24th hour of heating. However,
319 after this point, a more significant increase in viscosity was noticed in the enriched oils
320 compared to the control, particularly in the oil enriched at the highest level. This trend is
321 consistent with the higher degradation rate of linoleic acyl groups in SF05_170
322 compared to SF0_170 and SF01_170. At the endpoint of the experiment, the viscosity
323 of the control oil was boosted by 46.2%, while the oils enriched at 0.1 and 0.5% showed
324 increases of 47.7% and 51.5%, respectively.

325 The results obtained in the current study clearly indicate that polymerisation reactions
326 are favoured at frying temperatures in the presence of TNE, which contrasts with
327 previous studies investigating the effect of α -tocopherol, either alone or combined with
328 other isoforms, on frying oil performance (Lampi & Kamal-Eldin, 1998; Verlayen et al.,
329 2002; Nyström et al., 2007; Warner & Moser, 2009; Aladedunye & Przybylski, 2012;
330 Galanakis et al., 2018). However, Gertz et al. (2000) reported a higher percentage of
331 polymerised triglycerides (determined by HPLC) in sunflower and rapeseed oils heated
332 at 170 °C in the presence of added α -tocopherol at 0.25%. More recently, Kmiecik et al.
333 (2019) also observed increased polymerisation at 170 °C in rapeseed oils with higher
334 tocopherol content. The observed differences in frying oil viscosity may raise concerns
335 due to their potential negative impact on human health. Specifically, frying food in
336 more viscous oil can lead to food of lower quality and safety, as the higher oil uptake
337 (Blumenthal et al. 1991; Dobarganes et al., 2000; Achir et al., 2009) increases not only

338 the caloric content of the product but also the presence of oxidation products that may
339 be ingested and subsequently absorbed (Marquez-Ruiz & Dobarganes, 2007).

340 **3.1.4. Differences in the evolution of specific minor components in sunflower oil** 341 **analysed by DI-SPME-GC/MS**

342 When sunflower oil is subjected to frying conditions, both major and minor components
343 undergo degradation. Enrichment of the oil with TNE may also influence the
344 concentration changes of these components. To gain a deeper understanding of the
345 effect of TNE, the evolution of key minor components, including squalene, sterols and
346 tocopherols (both naturally present and added), was studied in non-enriched and
347 enriched sunflower oils.

348 *Degradation of squalene and sterols.* The abundances of squalene and the main sterols
349 present in sunflower oil (β -sitosterol, cycloartenol, cyclolaudenol and citrostadienol)
350 decreased in all samples overtime, fitting a linear equation with a high correlation
351 coefficient, as shown in **Table 1**.

352 Notably, there were differences in the degradation rate (coefficient **b**) of squalene
353 between non-enriched and enriched oils, regardless of the enrichment level. In fact, this
354 degradation rate in SF0_170 was almost twice as low as that observed in SF01_170 and
355 SF05_170, indicating that TNE addition promoted the degradation of squalene rather
356 than preventing it. Overall, at the experiment endpoint, the degradation of this
357 compound in SF0_170 accounted for 15.6%, whereas in SF01_170 and SF05_170, the
358 values were 27.1% and 26.8%, respectively. Regarding the main sterols, TNE also
359 favoured their degradation under frying conditions. In non-enriched sunflower oil,
360 degradation percentages ranged from 13.5 to 27.3%, while in the enriched samples, the
361 degradation was higher (26.3-35.6% for SF01_170 and 30.2-44.6% for SF05_170).

362 These findings align with the sterol degradation rates observed in **Table 1** where rates
363 in SF0_170 were approximately half those in SF0_170.

364 To our knowledge, this is the first study to examine the effect of tocopherol addition on
365 the degradation of minor components in frying oils. Tabee et al. (2008) reported that
366 enrichment of refined olive oil with α -tocopherol inhibited the formation of some
367 phytosterols oxidation products, although they did not monitor the concentrations of the
368 parent compounds.

369 ***Degradation of tocopherols and identification of derived metabolites.*** The decrease in
370 the abundances of the various tocopherols (α , γ , β , and δ isoforms) over time followed a
371 linear trend, with a high correlation coefficient, indicating that their degradation during
372 frying conditions conformed to a zero-order kinetic model. While some studies have
373 suggested that a first-order kinetic model better describes the degradation of tocopherols
374 when dissolved in glycerol and heated at 100-250 °C (Chung, 2007), in the present
375 study, the first-order kinetic model showed relatively poorer correlation coefficients
376 (data not shown) compared to the zero-order model. These findings suggest that, under
377 the conditions of this experiment, a zero-order model more accurately reflects the
378 degradation kinetics of tocopherols.

379 As expected, the predominant tocopherol in non-enriched sunflower oil was the α
380 isoform, followed by β and γ isoforms (see coefficient **a** in **Table 1**). δ -tocopherol was
381 present at such low concentrations that it was not detectable, but it was found in
382 SF01_170 and SF05_170 as a result of enrichment with the natural extract (Alberdi-
383 Cedeño et al., 2019). Notably, the *α -isoform*, which was present in the highest
384 concentration, was the most susceptible to thermo-degradation, decomposing much
385 faster than the other tocopherols. This observation aligns with previous studies that have
386 investigated the evolution of tocopherols in oils subjected to frying conditions (Lampi

387 & Kamal-Eldin, 1998; Marmesat et al., 2008b; Warner & Moser, 2009; Aladedunye &
388 Przybylski, 2012; Kmiecik et al., 2018; Athanasiadis et al., 2023). Additionally, the
389 degradation rate of each tocopherol was highest in SF05_170 and lowest in SF0_170,
390 likely due to the initial tocopherol content in each oil sample (coefficient **a**). This is
391 consistent with the findings of Marmesat et al. (2008b), who highlighted that both the
392 tocopherol content in the frying oil and the relative proportions of individual
393 tocopherols are critical factors in their degradation rates.

394 As tocopherols degrade at 170 °C, derived compounds are generated (see **Figures 5a**
395 and **b**). A total of seven metabolites were identified, including prist-1-ene (P), 6,10,14-
396 trimethylpentadecan-2-one (TrMPD), 4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide
397 (TeMHD) and 3,7,11-trimethyl-3-dodecanol (TrMD), which are common to all
398 tocopherol isoforms. In contrast, α -tocopherylquinone-2,3-epoxide (TQ23E), 5-formyl-
399 7,8-dimethyltolcol (5F78DT) and 7-formyl-5,8-dimethyltolcol (7F58DT) are specifically
400 linked to the α isoform (Nagata et al., 1999; Al-Malaika et al., 2001; Alberdi-Cedeño et
401 al., 2019), the predominant isoform in the natural extract used in the present study. The
402 fragments (m/z) and chemical structures of the detected metabolites are provided in
403 **Table S8** of the Supplementary Material. Some of these compounds were already
404 detectable prior to heating (see values for hour 0 in **Figures 5a** and **5b**), with higher
405 abundances being observed in enriched oils compared to the non-enriched, in a dose
406 dependent manner. This suggests that the TNE could have been slightly oxidised before
407 the experiment, a hypothesis that was confirmed by DI-SPME-GC/MS analysis of the
408 natural extract itself.

409 As shown in **Figures 5a** and **5b**, the abundance of these seven metabolites increased
410 throughout the heating experiment, indicating their generation as a consequence of
411 tocopherol degradation. At the experiment's endpoint, P exhibited the highest

412 abundances in all oil samples (both non-enriched and enriched), nearly twice as high as
413 those of TrMPD and TeMHD. TQ23E and TrMD were also generated at 170 °C in both
414 non-enriched and enriched oils, though to a much lesser extent in comparison to the
415 former metabolites. In addition to these tocopherol-metabolites, the formation of two
416 formyl derivatives was observed from hour 54 onwards, exclusively in the oil samples
417 enriched at the highest level (SF05_170). These derivatives might have also been
418 generated in SF0_170 and SF01_170, although at abundances below the detection limit
419 of the technique. Notably, the abundance of 5F78DT was nearly twice that of 7F58DT,
420 which aligns with the findings of Nilsson et al. (1968), who observed a preferential
421 formation of oxidation products derived from reactions at the 5-position of tocopherols
422 over the 7-position in fresh maize oil, due to the directing effect of the heterocyclic ring.
423 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of formyl derivatives being detected
424 as tocopherol degradation metabolites in foods. Both compounds have been previously
425 identified as oxidation products of α tocopherol during polyolefin melting, associated
426 with changes in polymer coloration (Nagata et al., 1999; Al-Malaika et al., 2001). Pirisi
427 et al. (1998) also identified 5F78DT as the main photolysis product of α isoform in
428 various model systems (hexane, anhydrous n-hexane and triolein). Whether the
429 generation of these tocopherol degradation products could pose a health concern, similar
430 to the oxidation products of phytosterol, remains to be determined.

431 **3.2. Effect of tocopherol natural extract (TNE) on sunflower oil stability under** 432 **accelerated storage conditions (70 °C with aeration)**

433 Considering that TNE did not enhance the stability of sunflower oil at frying conditions,
434 as opposed to previous reports, the same enriched and non-enriched oils were subjected
435 to accelerated storage conditions. The endpoint for this assessment was defined as the
436 day when total polymerisation was achieved; specifically, 10 days for SF0_70 and 13

437 days for enriched oils (SF01_70 and SF05_70). Unlike the observations under frying
438 conditions—enrichment with TNE delayed polymerisation under mild heating, in
439 agreement with the findings of other authors (Fuster et al., 1998; Marquez-Ruiz et al.,
440 2003; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022a,b). However, at moderate temperatures, oxidative
441 reactions predominate over polymerisation. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of
442 polyunsaturated acyl groups degradation and the formation of several oxidation
443 products was conducted.

444 **3.2.1. Differences in linoleic acyl group degradation**

445 **Figure 2b** shows the molar percentage evolution of linoleic acyl groups in the different
446 sunflower oils (SF0_70, SF01_70 and SF05_70) during oxidation under accelerated
447 storage conditions. As illustrated in **Figure 2a**, the overall evolution of linoleic acyl
448 groups in non-enriched and enriched oils differs significantly from that observed under
449 frying conditions, displaying three different linear stages rather than a single one. This
450 three-stage pattern aligns with previous studies on sunflower oil under similar
451 conditions (Guillén & Goicoechea, 2010; Martínez-Yusta & Guillén, 2019; Caño-Ochoa
452 et al., 2022a). The first two stages followed linear trends with high correlation
453 coefficients ($R > 0.9189$). In the initial phase, linoleic degradation occurred very slowly
454 in all samples. TNE addition extended the duration of this initial stage (from 5 days in
455 SF0_70 to 6 days in SF01_70 and SF05_70), although it increased the degradation rate
456 of linoleic groups in a dose dependent manner (-0.5615 , -0.8652 and $-1.1043\% \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$
457 for SF0_70, SF01_70 and SF05_70, respectively). During the second stage, degradation
458 accelerated significantly, lasting four days across all samples. Here, higher TNE levels
459 reduced the degradation rates of linoleic acyl groups (-10.2710 , -10.2580 and -9.0471%
460 $\cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ for SF0_70, SF01_70 and SF05_70, respectively). In the final stage,
461 degradation slowed again until total polymerisation occurred. In summary, TNE

462 accelerated linoleic degradation in the initial oxidation phase but slowed it in the second
463 stage, with the effect depending on concentration (see intensity of signal **a** in **Figure 6**).
464 This dual-phase behaviour highlights the importance of endpoint selection when
465 assessing the performance of TNE. These results are in line with those observed for the
466 addition of pure α or γ -tocopherol to sunflower and walnut oils under similar heating
467 conditions as in the current work (Martínez-Yusta & Guillén, 2019; Caño-Ochoa et al.,
468 2022ab).

469 **3.2.2. Differences in the formation of the main oxidation products detected by ^1H** 470 **NMR**

471 *Generation of monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates.* The accelerated
472 storage conditions caused the degradation of linoleic acyl groups, leading initially to the
473 formation of primary oxidation compounds, namely, monohydroperoxy-
474 octadecadienoates exhibiting conjugated dienic structures with either Z,E or E,E
475 isomerism (see signals **b** and **c** in **Figure 6**). In contrast to that observed at frying
476 conditions, these were not immediately degraded, and thus could be detected and
477 quantified. The evolution of the concentration of both isomers throughout the process is
478 represented in **Figures 7a** and **7b**. As can be observed, in non-enriched oil samples
479 (SF0_70), the concentration of Z,E isomers was higher than that of E,E at the beginning
480 of storage. From day 5 onwards, however, the concentration of the latter increased
481 significantly, surpassing that of the former, with both reaching their maximum
482 concentration after six days (23.8 ± 0.5 and 55.8 ± 0.8 mmol/mol AG, respectively).
483 Nevertheless, the enrichment of oil with the TNE caused an increase in the formation
484 rate of Z,E -monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates in a dose dependent
485 manner, which is consistent with the higher degradation of linoleic acyl groups observed
486 in enriched oils during the first stage of the oxidation process. At the same time, the

487 enrichment with the extract impairs the isomerisation to *E,E* isomers. Consequently, the
488 formation of these is delayed, so that at the highest enrichment level (0.5%), the
489 concentration of *E,E* isomers reaches its maximum value two days later than that of *Z,E*-
490 isomers. These results are in agreement with previous studies by other authors (Koskas
491 et al., 1984; Mäkinen et al., 2000, 2001; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022ab).

492 **Generation of monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates.** Under these accelerated
493 storage conditions, the primary oxidation compounds mentioned above degrade, leading
494 to the formation of several secondary or further oxidation products. Among these are
495 monoketo-octadecadienoates with *Z,E* and *E,E* isomerism in the conjugated dienic
496 structure (signals **d** and **e** in **Figure 6**). **Figures 7c** and **7d** show the evolution of their
497 concentrations throughout the oxidation process at 70 °C. In SF0_70, both isomer types
498 are detected after three days of heating, with maximum concentrations reached after
499 eight days (1.7 ± 0.2 and 5.2 ± 0.1 mmol/ mol AG for *Z,E* and *E,E* isomers,
500 respectively). It is important to note that only the *E,E* isomer was detected at frying
501 conditions. Enriching the oil with the lowest TNE concentration (0.1%) delayed the
502 formation of these compounds by one day (day 4 instead of day 3). However, the
503 maximum concentration of both compounds was still achieved on the same heating day
504 as in SF0_70 (day 8). A higher TNE concentration (0.5%) favoured the formation of *Z,E*
505 over *E,E* isomers, mirroring the pattern observed for monohydroperoxy-conjugated
506 octadecadienoates. Specifically, *Z,E*-monoketo-octadecadienoates were detected after
507 three days (one day before the *E,E* isomers) with their maximum concentration reached
508 on day 8. In contrast, the maximum concentration of *E,E*-monoketo-octadecadienoates
509 was achieved two days later (on day 10). A similar trend was observed when pure α and
510 γ -tocopherol was added to sunflower and walnut oils subjected to the same heating
511 conditions (Martínez-Yusta et al., 2019; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022a,b).

512 **Generation of aldehydes of different nature.** The evolution of their concentrations over
513 heating time is shown in **Figure 8**. As observed, during accelerated storage at 70 °C, the
514 types of aldehydes formed were consistent across enriched (SF01_70 and SF05_70) and
515 non-enriched oils (SF0_70), with similar relative proportions. In all three sunflower oils,
516 the aldehydes generated in the highest proportions were *E*-2-alkenals, 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-
517 alkenals and alkanals, followed by 4-hydroperoxy-*E*-2-alkenals, *E,E*-2,4-alkadienals,
518 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals, 4-oxo-2-alkenals and *E,Z*-2,4-alkadienals (signals **g-m** in
519 **Figure 6**). The aldehyde profile generated under these conditions differed from that
520 observed under frying conditions (see **Figure 3**). Indeed, during storage, the generation
521 of oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes was favoured.

522 However, the addition of TNE influenced the timing of aldehyde detection and their
523 evolution throughout the process. Overall, the generation of the several aldehydes was
524 slightly delayed in the enriched oils compared to SF0_70, particularly at the highest
525 enrichment level. Specifically, in both enriched samples, the formation of *E,Z*-2,4-
526 alkadienals, 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals and 4-oxo-2-alkenals was delayed by one day,
527 appearing after seven days instead of six. At the highest enrichment level (SF05_70),
528 the generation of 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-alkenals was also delayed by one day, occurring after
529 four days instead of three . This delay is associated to the above-mentioned evolution of
530 their precursors, monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates. For instance, on day
531 8, the concentration of conjugated *E,E*-monohydroperoxy-octadecadienoates was higher
532 in SF05_70 (58.3 mmol/mol AG) compared to SF01_70 and SF0_70 (49.4 and 27.7
533 mmol/mol AG, respectively) (see **Figure 7b**). By contrast, the opposite trend was
534 observed for *E*-2-alkenals, with concentrations of 3.47 mmol/mol AG in SF05_70
535 compared to 5.33 and 6.78 mmol/mol AG in SF01_70 and SF0_70, respectively. Hence,
536 the slower the hydroperoxide degradation, the later the aldehyde formation. These

537 results are in agreement with previous studies on the effect of α -tocopherol on the
538 oxidative stability of rapeseed oil triacylglycerols at 40 °C (Lampi, et al., 1999) and of
539 walnut and sunflower oils at 70 °C (Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022ab).

540 ***Generation of other oxidation compounds.*** In contrast to the heating conditions at
541 frying temperatures, these mild heating conditions led to the formation of other
542 oxidation compounds different to those mentioned above. Notably, the early generation
543 of non-conjugated *E,E*-dihydroperoxy-octadecadienoates was observed, with their
544 formation somewhat favoured in enriched oils, as occurred with monohydroperoxides.
545 These compounds can thus be considered as “pseudo-primary oxidation compounds”.
546 As the oxidation process progressed, several oxidation products containing an epoxy
547 group were formed, with *Z*-monoepoxy-octadecadienoates being the most abundant. In
548 addition, formic acid, compounds with a formate group and hydroxy-containing
549 products, such as dihydroxy-monoenes and monoether-mono-hydroxy-monoenes
550 structures, also appeared. Overall, the generation of these secondary oxidation products
551 was delayed when adding TNE, which is consistent with the delayed generation of most
552 aldehydes, suggesting that their formation results from further degradation of
553 hydroperoxides.

554 **3.2.3. Differences in the evolution of certain minor components in sunflower oil** 555 **analysed by DI-SPME-GC/MS**

556 As previously described for frying experiments at 170 °C in the absence of food, the
557 abundances of squalene, main sterols and tocopherols also decreased during storage at
558 70 °C, with a high correlation coefficient to linear equations (see **Table 2**). This is in
559 line with a previous study, where the degradation of minor components in corn oil
560 during accelerated storage was shown to follow a zero-order kinetic model (Alberdi-
561 Cedeño et al., 2019).

562 *Degradation of squalene and sterols.* In contrast to that observed at frying
563 temperatures, the addition of TNE to sunflower oil slowed the degradation of these
564 lipidic molecules of nutritional interest, indicating a protective effect against their
565 oxidation. As shown in **Table 2**, the degradation rates of squalene and β -sitosterol were
566 almost three times lower in SF05_70 compared to SF0_70. It is also important to note
567 that the degradation rate (coefficient **b**) of these minor compounds was higher under
568 accelerated storage than at frying conditions (see **Tables 1** and **2**). This can be explained
569 by \dagger the higher oxygen availability during storage, which promotes the oxidation of
570 these compounds.

571 *Degradation of tocopherols and identification of derived metabolites.* As observed
572 during frying conditions, a strong relationship was found between the initial abundance
573 of each tocopherol (coefficient **a** in **Table 2**) and its degradation rate at 70 °C
574 (coefficient **b**); higher initial tocopherol isoform content was associated with higher
575 degradation rates. These results are in line with those reported in a previous study on the
576 oxidation of minor compounds in different vegetable oils subjected to the same storage
577 conditions (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2019; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022a).

578 Regarding tocopherol-derived metabolites, the same seven compounds identified
579 previously were observed in the samples, although their relative proportions varied. As
580 shown in **Figures 5c** and **5d**, under these conditions, the compound present in the
581 highest abundances was TeMHD, followed by P, TrMPD and TrMD (which are
582 generated at similar levels, in contrast to that observed during frying conditions), with
583 TQ23E forming in the lowest abundance. The detection of 5F78DT and 7F58DT was
584 limited to sunflower oil samples enriched at the highest concentration, and these
585 compounds were generated at a comparable ratio (\approx 2:1). A similar pattern of tocopherol
586 degradation was observed during accelerated storage of corn oil, although the formation

587 of both formyl derivatives was not reported (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2019). These results
588 suggest that depending on the conditions to which the oil is subjected, specific
589 tocopherol degradation pathways may be preferentially activated, leading to distinct
590 profiles of tocopherol oxidation products.

591 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

592
593 The multi-faceted study conducted in the present work provided a comprehensive
594 overview, highlighting the differential effects of a tocopherol natural extract on the
595 major and minor components of sunflower oil subjected to frying and accelerated
596 storage conditions. Under frying conditions, none of the concentrations tested enhanced
597 oil stability; rather, the opposite effect was observed. Specifically, higher enrichment
598 levels led to increased degradation of both linoleic acyl groups and minor
599 components of interest, such as squalene, sterols and tocopherols. Additionally,
600 viscosity results suggested that polymerisation reactions were slightly enhanced in the
601 presence of the extract. This is an important consideration, as it may negatively impact
602 human health due to the increased absorption of frying oil by food. Furthermore, a
603 selective generation of secondary oxidation products was observed in oils enriched with
604 the tocopherol natural extract.

605 By contrast, under accelerated storage conditions, TNE displayed a more complex
606 effect. In the initial stages, it promoted the degradation of polyunsaturated linoleic
607 groups, as well as the formation of the derived primary oxidation products, such as *Z,E*-
608 monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates. However, the isomerisation to *E,E*
609 isomers and the subsequent decomposition into secondary and further oxidation
610 products was delayed. Moreover, in the presence of the extract, the degradation rate of
611 linoleic acyl groups during the second stage was lower compared to the non-enriched oil
612 sample. Similarly, the degradation rates of minor components were also reduced, and oil

613 polymerisation was impaired. Therefore, to draw solid conclusions about the effects of
614 adding compounds with potential antioxidant activity, caution must be exercised when
615 selecting the number and types of parameters used to assess oil stability.

616 Furthermore, it has been reported for the first time that differences in the profile of
617 tocopherol metabolites occur depending on thermo-oxidative conditions, suggesting
618 variation in their degradation pathways. DI-SPME-GC/MS enabled the identification of
619 formyl derivatives in enriched oils, which had not been previously described. Therefore,
620 future research should focus on the potential effects of tocopherol metabolites on both
621 food quality and human health.

622 Finally, it must be noted that, whenever an antioxidant of natural origin shows a
623 protective effect, the comparison of its performance with that of widely used synthetic
624 antioxidants would be of great interest for practical reasons since it would help to better
625 evaluate its potential application in food industry. However, as the TNE assayed did not
626 improve the stability of sunflower oil under the processing conditions employed, this
627 comparison was not conducted in this work.

628 **Author contributions**

629 **Jon Alberdi-Cedeño:** Conceptualisation, Investigation, Visualisation, Formal analysis,
630 Writing-Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing & Editing, Funding acquisition;

631 **Andrea Martínez-Yusta:** Formal analysis, Writing-Original draft preparation, Writing-
632 Reviewing & Editing, Funding acquisition; **Ainhoa Ruiz-Aracama:** Conceptualisation,

633 Investigation, Writing- Reviewing & Editing, Funding acquisition; **Encarnación**

634 **Goicoechea-Oses:** Conceptualisation, Investigation, Writing- Reviewing & Editing,

635 Funding acquisition, Project Administration; **Barbara Nieva-Echevarría:**

636 Conceptualisation, Investigation, Visualisation, Formal analysis, Writing-Original draft
637 preparation, Writing- Reviewing & Editing, Funding acquisition.

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646

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FIGURES

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectra of sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170) and 0.5% (SF05_170) before (0 hours) and after being subjected to frying conditions (138 hours, 170 °C). The letters of the signals correspond to those indicated in Table S1. **a**: linoleic acyl groups; **c**: *Z,E*-monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates; **d**: *E,E*-monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates; **f₁** and **f₂**: *E,E*-2,4-alkadienals; **g**: *E*-2-alkenals; **h**: 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals; **i**: 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-alkenals; **k**: *E,Z*-2,4-alkadienals; **l**: alkanals; **n**: 4-oxo-alkanals.

Figure 2. Evolution of the molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups, determined by ^1H NMR, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0 -□-) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01 -△-) and 0.5% (SF05 -○-), subjected to: a) frying conditions at 170 °C and b) accelerated storage at 70 °C.

Figure 3. Evolution of the concentration of several oxidation products determined by ^1H NMR in non-enriched (SF0_170 -□-) and enriched sunflower oil with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170 -Δ-) and 0.5% (SF05_170 -○-) during frying conditions at 170 °C.

Figure 4. Evolution of viscosity, determined by rotational viscometer and expressed as $\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, in non-enriched (SFO_170 -□-) and enriched sunflower oil with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170 -Δ-) and 0.5% (SF05_170 -○-) during frying conditions at 170 °C.

Figure 5. Evolution of abundances of the several tocopherol-derived metabolites, detected by DI-SPME-GC/MS, in: a) non-enriched and b) enriched sunflower oil with the assayed tocopherol natural extract at 0.5% during frying conditions at 170 °C and c) non-enriched and d) enriched sunflower oil with the assayed tocopherol natural extract at 0.5% during accelerated storage at 70 °C. P: Prist-1-ene; TrMPD: 6,10,14-trimethylpentadecan-2-one; TeMHPD: 4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide; TrMD: 3,7,11-trimethyl-3-dodecanol; TQ23E: α -tocopherylquinone-2,3-epoxide; 5F78DT: 5-formyl-7,8-dimethyltocol; 7F58DT: 7-formyl-5,8-dimethyltocol.

Figure 6. ^1H NMR spectra of sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70) and 0.5% (SF05_70) before (day 0) and after being subjected to accelerated storage conditions (70 °C) for 8 days and 10 or 13 days (endpoint). The letters of the signals correspond to those indicated in Table S1. **a:** linoleic acyl groups; **b:** *E,E*-monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates; **c:** *Z,E*-monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates; **d:** *E,E*-monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates; **e:** *Z,E*-monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates; **f₂:** *E,E*-2,4-alkadienals; **g:** *E*-2-alkenals; **h:** 4,5-epoxy-*E*-2-alkenals; **i:** 4-hydroxy-*E*-2-alkenals; **j:** 4-hydroperoxy-*E*-2-alkenals; **k:** *E,Z*-2,4-alkadienals; **l:** alkanals; **m:** 4-oxo-*E*-2-alkenals.

Figure 7. Evolution of the concentration of hydroperoxy-octadecadienoates and keto-octadecadienoates, determined by ^1H NMR, in non-enriched (SF0_70 -□-) and enriched sunflower oil with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70 -Δ-) and 0.5% (SF05_70 -○-) during accelerated storage at 70 °C.

Figure 8. Evolution of de concentration of aldehydes, determined by ^1H NMR, in non-enriched (SF0_70 -□-) and enriched sunflower oil with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70 -Δ-) and 0.5% (SF05_70 -○-) during accelerated storage at 70 °C.

1 **Table 1.** Coefficients of the linear equations that relate the decrease of the abundances (AB) of squalene, sterols and tocopherols with the experiment time (t;
 2 expressed as number of hours) ($AB = a + b*t$), together with the correlation coefficients during heating at 170 °C of sunflower oil, either non-enriched
 3 (SF0_170) or enriched with tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% and 0.5% (SF01_170 and SF05_170).
 4

	SF0_170			SF01_170			SF05_170		
	a	b	R	a	b	R	a	b	R
Squalene*	75.125	-0.1217	0.9523	93.610	-0.2292	0.9193	97.664	-0.2472	0.9814
Sterols									
β-sitosterol*	4.3024	-0.0059	0.9782	4.5113	-0.0110	0.9703	4.1570	-0.0159	0.9648
Cycloartenol*	1.8504	-0.0051	0.9715	1.8653	-0.0058	0.9907	1.8705	-0.0064	0.9825
Cyclolaudenol*	3.5608	-0.0069	0.9695	3.4637	-0.0084	0.9992	3.4006	-0.0122	0.9783
Citrostadienol*	1.2274	-0.0034	0.9758	1.2483	-0.0040	0.9711	1.2243	-0.0063	0.9927
Tocopherols									
α-tocopherol*	51.794	-0.1323	0.9895	69.440	-0.2627	0.9410	139.15	-0.3234	0.9377
γ-tocopherol*	0.4922	-0.0036	0.9785	10.437	-0.0694	0.9960	36.928	-0.1737	0.9833
β-tocopherol*	2.8215	-0.0127	0.9682	3.3889	-0.0136	0.9685	4.7391	-0.0138	0.9634
δ-tocopherol*	-	-	-	7.7376	-0.0273	0.9601	28.519	-0.0644	0.9259

5 *Asterisked compounds were acquired commercially and used as standards for identification purposes; -: not detected.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Different effects of tocopherol natural extract on sunflower oil stability under frying and accelerated storage conditions: A comprehensive study on the fate of major and minor components of oil, and added tocopherols

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Table S1. Chemical shifts, multiplicities and assignments of the ^1H NMR signals in CDCl_3 of protons in main acyl groups and some oxidation compounds present in the different oil samples. The signal letters agree with those given in **Figures 1** and **6**.

Signal	Chemical shift (ppm)	Multiplicity	Type of protons	Functional group	Compound
MAIN ACYL GROUPS					
a	2.77 ^a	t	=HC- <u>CH</u> ₂ -CH=		Linoleic acyl groups
	2.23-2.36 ^a	dt	-OCO- <u>CH</u> ₂ -		Acyl groups
OXIDATION COMPOUNDS					
b	6.27 ^b	ddm	- <u>CH</u> = <u>CH</u> - <u>CH</u> = <u>CH</u> -		<i>E,E</i> -monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates
c	6.58 ^b	dddd	- <u>CH</u> = <u>CH</u> - <u>CH</u> = <u>CH</u> -		<i>Z,E</i> -monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates
d	7.13 ^c	dm	-CO-CH= <u>CH</u> -CH=CH-		<i>E,E</i> -monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates
e	7.49 ^c	ddd	-CO-CH= <u>CH</u> -CH=CH-		<i>Z,E</i> -monoketo-conjugated octadecadienoates
f₁	7.09 ^d	m	CHO-CH= <u>CH</u> -		<i>E,E</i> -2,4-alkadienals
f₂	9.52 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		
g	9.49 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		<i>E</i> -2-alkenals
h	9.55 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		4,5-epoxy- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals
i	9.57 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		4-hydroxy- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals
j	9.58 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		4-hydroperoxy- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals
k	9.60 ^d	d	- <u>CHO</u>		<i>E,Z</i> -2,4-alkadienals
l	9.75 ^d	t	- <u>CHO</u>		alkanals
m	9.77 ^d	d	<u>CHO</u>		4-oxo- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals
n	9.78 ^e	t	- <u>CHO</u>		4-oxo-alkanals

Abbreviations: t: triplet; d: doublet; m: multiplet.

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^dData taken from:

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Table S2. Molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170) and 0.5% (SF05_170) during heating at 170 °C. The data correspond to those in Figure 2a. Different letters within each row for each heating time indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (hours)	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170
0	57.6 ± 0.2 ^a	57.7 ± 0.0a	57.7 ± 0.1a
6	57.4 ± 0.0a	57.3 ± 0.0a	57.4 ± 0.1a
12	57.0 ± 0.3 ^a	56.9 ± 0.2a	56.9 ± 0.7a
18	56.3 ± 0.0a	56.4 ± 0.8a	56.3 ± 0.2a
24	55.7 ± 0.1 ^a	55.9 ± 0.0a	55.6 ± 0.2a
36	54.7 ± 0.5 ^a	54.6 ± 0.0a	54.2 ± 0.5a
42	54.3 ± 0.1 ^a	54.1 ± 0.1a	53.6 ± 0.0b
48	53.7 ± 0.1 ^a	53.9 ± 0.3a	53.1 ± 0.0b
54	53.4 ± 0.1 ^a	53.4 ± 0.2a	52.6 ± 0.4b
60	53.0 ± 0.2 ^a	52.9 ± 0.1a	52.2 ± 0.3b
78	51.7 ± 0.2 ^a	51.7 ± 0.3a	51.1 ± 0.0b
90	50.9 ± 0.1 ^a	50.6 ± 0.0a	49.9 ± 0.0b
102	50.0 ± 0.0a	49.9 ± 0.3a	49.0 ± 0.1b
120	48.9 ± 0.2a	48.8 ± 0.2a	48.0 ± 0.0b
138	47.6 ± 0.0a	47.3 ± 0.0a	46.6 ± 0.1b

Table S3. Molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70) and 0.5% (SF05_70) during accelerated storage at 70 °C. The data correspond to those in Figure 2b. Different letters within each row for each heating time indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (days)	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70
0	57.2 ± 0.1 ^a	57.0 ± 0.1 ^a	57.1 ± 0.2 ^a
1	57.1 ± 0.2 ^a	57.2 ± 0.3 ^a	56.8 ± 0.0 ^a
2	56.5 ± 0.5 ^a	56.2 ± 0.2 ^a	55.7 ± 0.5 ^a
3	55.8 ± 0.0 ^a	56.0 ± 0.2 ^a	54.2 ± 0.0 ^b
4	55.4 ± 0.1 ^a	55.3 ± 0.4 ^a	52.9 ± 0.0 ^b
5	54.5 ± 0.1 ^a	53.8 ± 0.5 ^a	51.5 ± 0.1 ^b
6	42.8 ± 0.4 ^a	51.4 ± 0.1 ^b	51.2 ± 0.0 ^b
7	31.1 ± 0.0 ^a	42.0 ± 0.8 ^b	42.8 ± 0.0 ^b
8	20.7 ± 0.1 ^a	25.6 ± 0.5 ^b	33.4 ± 0.2 ^c
9	12.0 ± 0.0 ^a	17.6 ± 0.0 ^b	24.1 ± 0.3 ^c
10	9.4 ± 0.2 ^a	12.3 ± 0.3 ^b	15.3 ± 0.3 ^c
11		8.2 ± 0.0 ^a	9.8 ± 0.7 ^b
12		5.1 ± 0.2 ^a	5.8 ± 0.5 ^a
13		5.2 ± 0.9 ^a	7.0 ± 0.3 ^b

Table S4. Concentration of several oxidation products, determined by ¹H NMR and expressed as mmol/mol TG, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170) and 0.5% (SF05_170) during heating at 170 °C. The data correspond to those in Figures 3a-d. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference (*p* < 0.05) among samples.

Time (hours)	<i>E,E</i> -keto-octadecadienoates			<i>E,E</i> -2,4-alkadienals			<i>E</i> -2-alkenals			alkanals		
	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170
0	-	-	-	0.06 ± 0.02a	0.10 ± 0.02a	0.08 ± 0.02a	0.12 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.00a	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.18 ± 0.00a	0.17 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.00a
6	-	-	-	0.39 ± 0.00a	0.34 ± 0.00a	0.38 ± 0.14a	0.20 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.00a	0.26 ± 0.00a	0.23 ± 0.01a	0.24 ± 0.00a
12	0.26 ± 0.10a	0.14 ± 0.05a	0.18 ± 0.07a	0.62 ± 0.10a	0.52 ± 0.10a	0.59 ± 0.02a	0.31 ± 0.01a	0.22 ± 0.10ab	0.22 ± 0.02b	0.30 ± 0.02a	0.26 ± 0.05a	0.24 ± 0.10a
18	0.29 ± 0.03a	0.28 ± 0.01a	0.31 ± 0.05a	0.82 ± 0.30a	0.71 ± 0.05a	0.77 ± 0.08a	0.35 ± 0.00a	0.29 ± 0.01b	0.27 ± 0.08b	0.31 ± 0.12a	0.29 ± 0.02a	0.25 ± 0.07a
24	0.33 ± 0.01a	0.32 ± 0.00a	0.40 ± 0.12a	1.00 ± 0.00a	0.84 ± 0.20a	0.94 ± 0.05a	0.44 ± 0.02a	0.35 ± 0.00b	0.31 ± 0.06b	0.35 ± 0.08a	0.29 ± 0.03a	0.26 ± 0.07a
36	0.50 ± 0.10a	0.45 ± 0.14a	0.46 ± 0.22a	1.31 ± 0.02 ^a	1.07 ± 0.12b	1.20 ± 0.02b	0.55 ± 0.00a	0.46 ± 0.05b	0.40 ± 0.05b	0.37 ± 0.02a	0.33 ± 0.05a	0.29 ± 0.10a
42	0.53 ± 0.04a	0.51 ± 0.11a	0.54 ± 0.08a	1.47 ± 0.00a	1.18 ± 0.02b	1.33 ± 0.02a	0.63 ± 0.05a	0.53 ± 0.00b	0.45 ± 0.00c	0.39 ± 0.07a	0.34 ± 0.11a	0.30 ± 0.05a
48	0.52 ± 0.00a	0.49 ± 0.09a	0.56 ± 0.00a	1.60 ± 0.08 ^a	1.31 ± 0.05b	1.52 ± 0.04a	0.67 ± 0.16a	0.58 ± 0.07ab	0.50 ± 0.04b	0.43 ± 0.07a	0.38 ± 0.00a	0.33 ± 0.10a
54	0.51 ± 0.02a	0.55 ± 0.03a	0.55 ± 0.11a	1.78 ± 0.00a	1.46 ± 0.04b	1.65 ± 0.11a	0.74 ± 0.00a	0.63 ± 0.01b	0.56 ± 0.11b	0.51 ± 0.00a	0.41 ± 0.05b	0.38 ± 0.08b
60	0.51 ± 0.17a	0.50 ± 0.03a	0.57 ± 0.04a	1.86 ± 0.20 ^a	1.52 ± 0.10b	1.76 ± 0.10a	0.82 ± 0.00a	0.68 ± 0.00b	0.61 ± 0.00c	0.56 ± 0.04a	0.46 ± 0.00b	0.40 ± 0.00b
78	0.58 ± 0.12a	0.63 ± 0.15a	0.67 ± 0.12a	2.00 ± 0.04 ^a	1.70 ± 0.02b	1.92 ± 0.06a	0.94 ± 0.18a	0.80 ± 0.10b	0.67 ± 0.00c	0.71 ± 0.00a	0.56 ± 0.13b	0.51 ± 0.01b
90	0.61 ± 0.10a	0.63 ± 0.08a	0.67 ± 0.09a	2.09 ± 0.05 ^a	1.76 ± 0.06b	2.04 ± 0.00a	1.04 ± 0.00a	0.87 ± 0.05b	0.77 ± 0.02c	0.75 ± 0.12a	0.61 ± 0.00b	0.58 ± 0.10b
102	0.67 ± 0.12a	0.68 ± 0.00a	0.68 ± 0.04a	2.19 ± 0.36 ^a	1.89 ± 0.04b	2.10 ± 0.00a	1.06 ± 0.04a	0.90 ± 0.00b	0.80 ± 0.00c	0.82 ± 0.00a	0.64 ± 0.02b	0.62 ± 0.04b
120	0.65 ± 0.11a	0.69 ± 0.01a	0.66 ± 0.20a	2.17 ± 0.04 ^a	1.90 ± 0.00b	2.11 ± 0.10a	1.15 ± 0.00a	0.98 ± 0.02b	0.90 ± 0.06b	1.00 ± 0.00a	0.81 ± 0.04b	0.77 ± 0.05b
138	0.63 ± 0.04a	0.61 ± 0.02a	0.66 ± 0.01a	2.20 ± 0.25 ^a	1.93 ± 0.02b	2.11 ± 0.09a	1.21 ± 0.00a	1.13 ± 0.05b	0.90 ± 0.00c	1.01 ± 0.06a	0.87 ± 0.00b	0.77 ± 0.08b

Table S5. Concentration of several oxidation products, determined by ¹H NMR and expressed as mmol/mol TG, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170) and 0.5% (SF05_170) during heating at 170 °C. The data correspond to those in Figure 3e-h. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (hours)	<i>E,Z</i> -2,4-alkadienals			4-oxo-alkanals			4-hydroxy- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals			4,5-epoxy- <i>E</i> -2-alkenals		
	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170
0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	0.14 ± 0.03a	0.11 ± 0.03a	0.13 ± 0.00a	-	-	-	0.08 ± 0.01a	0.07 ± 0.02a	-	-	-	-
12	0.17 ± 0.01a	0.14 ± 0.03a	0.16 ± 0.05a	-	-	-	0.09 ± 0.00a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00b	-	-	-
18	0.19 ± 0.00a	0.17 ± 0.04a	0.19 ± 0.01a	-	-	-	0.08 ± 0.02a	0.07 ± 0.02a	0.09 ± 0.03a	0.05 ± 0.00	-	-
24	0.23 ± 0.02a	0.20 ± 0.05a	0.21 ± 0.05a	-	-	-	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.08 ± 0.00b	0.09 ± 0.00b	0.05 ± 0.00a	0.03 ± 0.00b	0.02 ± 0.01b
36	0.28 ± 0.00a	0.24 ± 0.00b	0.27 ± 0.02ab	-	-	0.03 ± 0.00	0.15 ± 0.02a	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00b	0.06 ± 0.02a	0.05 ± 0.02a	0.04 ± 0.01b
42	0.30 ± 0.00a	0.28 ± 0.00b	0.31 ± 0.00a	-	-	0.04 ± 0.00	0.17 ± 0.00a	0.14 ± 0.00b	0.11 ± 0.02bc	0.07 ± 0.02a	0.05 ± 0.04a	0.05 ± 0.00a
48	0.32 ± 0.02a	0.28 ± 0.00b	0.33 ± 0.08ab	-	0.04 ± 0.01a	0.06 ± 0.02a	0.18 ± 0.00a	0.15 ± 0.00b	0.12 ± 0.00c	0.07 ± 0.03a	0.06 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00a
54	0.33 ± 0.10a	0.30 ± 0.05a	0.35 ± 0.09a	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00b	0.07 ± 0.00c	0.18 ± 0.01a	0.15 ± 0.00ab	0.15 ± 0.03a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.07 ± 0.02a	0.06 ± 0.03a
60	0.34 ± 0.01a	0.31 ± 0.03a	0.36 ± 0.02a	0.05 ± 0.00a	0.06 ± 0.00b	0.09 ± 0.01c	0.19 ± 0.00a	0.15 ± 0.02b	0.14 ± 0.00b	0.08 ± 0.02a	0.08 ± 0.01a	0.06 ± 0.01a
78	0.36 ± 0.02a	0.33 ± 0.01b	0.38 ± 0.00c	0.07 ± 0.01 ^a	0.08 ± 0.02a	0.10 ± 0.02a	0.20 ± 0.00a	0.17 ± 0.00b	0.15 ± 0.03b	0.08 ± 0.02a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.07 ± 0.00a
90	0.35 ± 0.00a	0.34 ± 0.00b	0.39 ± 0.02a	0.08 ± 0.02 ^a	0.09 ± 0.02a	0.13 ± 0.01b	0.18 ± 0.03a	0.16 ± 0.03a	0.14 ± 0.02a	0.09 ± 0.03a	0.09 ± 0.02a	0.07 ± 0.01a
102	0.35 ± 0.08a	0.34 ± 0.10a	0.40 ± 0.04a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.16 ± 0.00b	0.17 ± 0.00a	0.18 ± 0.05a	0.16 ± 0.01a	0.09 ± 0.01a	0.10 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00a
120	0.36 ± 0.04a	0.36 ± 0.00a	0.39 ± 0.00ab	0.13 ± 0.04a	0.14 ± 0.01a	0.19 ± 0.00b	0.18 ± 0.00a	0.18 ± 0.00a	0.16 ± 0.01a	0.10 ± 0.03a	0.10 ± 0.02a	0.10 ± 0.01a
138	0.36 ± 0.02a	0.37 ± 0.00a	0.39 ± 0.00ab	0.16 ± 0.00a	0.17 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.00b	0.21 ± 0.05a	0.20 ± 0.09a	0.18 ± 0.05a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.10 ± 0.02a

Table S6. Evolution of viscosity, expressed as mPa*s-1, of sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_170) and 0.5% (SF05_170) during heating at 170 °C. The data correspond to those in Figure 4. Different letters within each row for each heating time indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (hours)	SF0_170	SF01_170	SF05_170
0	59.5 ± 0.1a	60.6 ± 0.2 ^a	60.9 ± 0.4a
12	63.4 ± 0.2a	62.6 ± 0.3 ^a	63.2 ± 0.2a
24	78.3 ± 0.2a	77.7 ± 0.4 ^a	78.4 ± 0.1a
42	77.5 ± 0.5a	80.6 ± 2.3 ^a	81.1 ± 0.6ab
54	88.4 ± 0.6a	88.1 ± 0.4 ^a	90.4 ± 0.1b
78	86.3 ± 0.5a	89.6 ± 0.9b	93.2 ± 0.5c
102	83.3 ± 0.0a	87.2 ± 0.6b	92.5 ± 0.9c
138	111.2 ± 0.8a	115.5 ± 0.4b	125.0 ± 0.5c

Table S7. Abundances of several tocopherol-derived metabolites, determined by DI-SPME-GC/MS, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_170) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.5% (SF05_170) during heating at 170 °C. The data correspond to those in Figure 5a,b. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between samples.

Time (hours)	P		TrMPD		TeMPD		TrMD		TQ23E		7F58DT		5F78DT	
	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170	SF0_170	SF0.5_170
0	10.9 ± 1.0a	37.1 ± 2.2b	-	0.5 ± 0.0	6.1 ± 0.2a	23.5 ± 3.1b	-	-	-	1.2 ± 0.0	-	-	-	-
24	12.9 ± 2.8a	40.2 ± 0.9b	10.4 ± 0.9a	25.0 ± 0.8b	8.3 ± 0.4a	23.7 ± 1.4b	-	2.7 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1a	1.5 ± 0.3a	-	-	-	-
54	20.3 ± 1.1a	47.5 ± 4.0b	16.8 ± 1.0a	26.3 ± 1.1b	9.8 ± 0.8a	26.3 ± 2.2b	0.8 ± 0.0a	3.4 ± 0.8b	2.0 ± 0.2a	1.9 ± 0.0a	-	0.2 ± 0.0	-	0.3 ± 0.0
102	26.0 ± 0.7a	49.8 ± 3.2b	17.2 ± 2.7a	28.2 ± 0.8b	13.3 ± 1.3a	27.5 ± 0.9b	1.6 ± 0.1a	3.6 ± 0.5b	2.8 ± 0.1a	2.4 ± 0.4a	-	0.2 ± 0.0	-	0.4 ± 0.0

P: Prist-1-ene; TrMPD: 6,10,14-trimethylpentadecan-2-one; TeMPD: 4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide; TrMD: 3,7,11-trimethyl-3-dodecanol; TQ23E: α -tocopherylquinone-2,3-epoxide; 5F78DT: 5-formyl-7,8-dimethyltolcol; 7F58DT: 7-formyl-5,8-dimethyltolcol.

Table S8. Tocopherol isoforms oxidation-derived metabolites identified by DI-SPME-GC/MS, together with their molecular weight, mass fragments (m/z) and chemical structures.

Compound (molecular weight)	Fragments (m/z)	Chemical structures
Prist-1-ene (P) (266)	41(68), 43(57), 55(87), 56(100), 57(95), 69(90), 70(75), 71(52), 83(47), 97(26), 111(47), 126(39), 196(10), 266(15)	
6,10,14-trimethylpentadecan-2-one (TrMPD) (268)	41(35), 43(100), 55(36), 57(37), 58(75), 71(47), 85(26), 95(21), 109(21), 123(17), 210(10), 250(20), 268(5)	
4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide (TeMHD) (324)	43(40), 55(25), 57(22), 69(21), 71(17), 99(100), 114(22), 126(21), 324(4)	
3,7,11-trimethyl-3-dodecanol (TrMD) (228)	43(19), 55(15), 57(15), 73(100), 83(13), 97(12), 111(12)	
α -tocopherylquinone-2,3-epoxide (TQ23E) (462)*	43(82), 71(20), 137(33), 152(62), 195(87), 237(100), 402(10)	

7-formyl-5,8-dimethyltocol (7F58DT) (444)*

43(14), 55(10), 178(22), 179(21),
180(12), 219(14), 444(100)

5-formyl-7,8-dimethyltocol (5F78DT) (444)*

43(25), 55(14), 57 (16), 151 (10),
179(39), 191(23), 201(79), 202(32),
219(20), 220(21), 426(12), 444(100)

*Compounds coming exclusively from α -tocopherol.

Table S9. Concentration of several oxidation products, determined by ¹H NMR and expressed as mmol/mol TG, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70) and 0.5% (SF05_70) subjected to accelerated storage conditions. The data correspond to those in Figure 7a-d. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (days)	<i>Z,E</i> -hydroperoxy-octadecadienoates			<i>E,E</i> -hydroperoxy-octadecadienoates			<i>Z,E</i> -keto-octadecadienoates			<i>E,E</i> -keto-octadecadienoates		
	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70
0	0.6 ± 0.2a	0.9 ± 0.3a	0.7 ± 0.1a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	2.0 ± 0.5a	2.5 ± 0.1a	5.4 ± 0.0b	0.7 ± 0.0a	0.8 ± 0.0a	0.9 ± 0.0a	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	4.3 ± 0.1a	5.3 ± 0.2b	11.3 ± 0.5c	2.4 ± 0.9a	1.9 ± 0.5a	2.0 ± 0.1a	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	7.2 ± 0.0a	9.9 ± 0.3b	22.0 ± 0.7c	4.0 ± 0.0a	4.1 ± 0.0a	5.2 ± 0.0a	0.22 ± 0.08a	-	0.28 ± 0.02a	0.35 ± 0.00	-	-
4	10.2 ± 0.3a	14.1 ± 0.2b	29.7 ± 1.1c	8.1 ± 0.0a	7.6 ± 0.4a	9.4 ± 0.1b	0.16 ± 0.00a	0.23 ± 0.01b	0.31 ± 0.01c	0.26 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.00b	0.25 ± 0.00a
5	11.4 ± 1.0a	15.7 ± 0.6b	28.5 ± 0.8c	13.8 ± 0.8a	13.5 ± 0.4a	21.2 ± 0.4b	0.49 ± 0.00a	0.39 ± 0.00b	0.59 ± 0.00c	0.14 ± 0.00a	0.40 ± 0.00b	0.52 ± 0.03c
6	23.8 ± 0.6a	17.7 ± 0.3b	31.2 ± 0.2c	55.8 ± 2.3a	30.1 ± 0.5b	19.2 ± 0.2c	1.11 ± 0.01a	0.63 ± 0.05b	0.77 ± 0.12b	1.69 ± 0.22a	0.64 ± 0.01b	0.45 ± 0.08c
7	22.8 ± 1.2a	24.3 ± 0.6a	23.1 ± 0.9a	44.2 ± 1.6a	58.4 ± 2.0b	51.1 ± 1.9c	1.47 ± 0.03a	1.09 ± 0.00b	1.08 ± 0.00b	4.16 ± 0.05a	2.06 ± 0.07b	1.37 ± 0.14c
8	14.5 ± 0.3a	18.4 ± 0.0b	23.1 ± 1.2c	27.7 ± 0.9a	49.4 ± 1.8b	58.3 ± 1.5c	1.66 ± 0.11a	1.68 ± 0.08a	1.46 ± 0.00b	5.21 ± 0.02a	5.84 ± 0.05b	3.26 ± 0.03c
9	-	-	16.7 ± 0.8	22.2 ± 0.7a	31.8 ± 0.9b	41.7 ± 1.1c	1.12 ± 0.00a	1.53 ± 0.00b	1.40 ± 0.00c	4.11 ± 0.05a	4.63 ± 0.09b	4.82 ± 0.02c
10	-	-	-	17.7 ± 0.3a	23.2 ± 0.2b	30.2 ± 0.5c	0.93 ± 0.05a	0.98 ± 0.05a	1.36 ± 0.12b	3.52 ± 0.05a	4.27 ± 0.05b	4.92 ± 0.10c
11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.70 ± 0.02a	0.81 ± 0.04b	-	3.41 ± 0.20a	3.99 ± 0.01b
12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.31 ± 0.00a	0.43 ± 0.03b	-	1.82 ± 0.00a	2.01 ± 0.00b
13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.24 ± 0.01a	0.42 ± 0.13b	-	2.05 ± 0.01a	2.31 ± 0.00b

Table S10. Concentration of several oxidation products, determined by ¹H NMR and expressed as mmol/mol TG, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70) and 0.5% (SF05_70) subjected to accelerated storage conditions. The data correspond to those in Figure 8a-d. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (days)	<i>E-2-alkenals</i>			<i>4-hydroxy-E-2-alkenals</i>			<i>alkanals</i>			<i>4-hydroperoxy-E-2-alkenals</i>		
	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70
0	0.14 ± 0.00a	0.14 ± 0.00a	0.17 ± 0.00a	-	-	-	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.00a	-	-	-
1	0.15 ± 0.05a	0.09 ± 0.04a	0.15 ± 0.05a	-	-	-	0.10 ± 0.02a	0.14 ± 0.03a	0.16 ± 0.05a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.07 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.01b
2	0.12 ± 0.03a	0.14 ± 0.01a	0.15 ± 0.02a	-	-	-	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.07 ± 0.00a
3	0.12 ± 0.02a	0.17 ± 0.08a	0.07 ± 0.05ab	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00a	-	0.13 ± 0.02a	0.14 ± 0.01a	0.12 ± 0.02a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00a
4	0.11 ± 0.05a	0.11 ± 0.04a	0.14 ± 0.02a	0.02 ± 0.00a	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00a	0.11 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.02a	0.14 ± 0.03a	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.06 ± 0.03a	0.12 ± 0.02b
5	0.13 ± 0.00a	0.15 ± 0.01a	0.24 ± 0.00b	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.06 ± 0.00b	0.10 ± 0.00c	0.21 ± 0.00a	0.12 ± 0.00b	0.13 ± 0.00b	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00a	0.16 ± 0.00b
6	1.06 ± 0.01a	0.35 ± 0.00b	0.15 ± 0.00c	0.54 ± 0.01a	0.14 ± 0.00b	0.08 ± 0.00c	0.50 ± 0.01a	0.13 ± 0.00b	0.13 ± 0.00b	1.28 ± 0.00a	0.33 ± 0.00b	0.14 ± 0.00c
7	3.42 ± 0.14a	1.21 ± 0.34b	1.05 ± 0.01b	2.53 ± 0.02a	0.65 ± 0.01b	0.51 ± 0.00c	2.43 ± 0.02a	0.86 ± 0.01b	0.64 ± 0.00c	2.70 ± 0.20a	1.50 ± 0.00b	1.26 ± 0.01c
8	6.78 ± 0.17a	5.33 ± 0.11b	3.47 ± 0.04c	6.52 ± 0.13a	4.80 ± 0.10b	2.77 ± 0.33c	2.73 ± 0.03a	2.70 ± 0.01b	1.56 ± 0.03c	4.05 ± 0.84a	3.70 ± 0.25ab	3.04 ± 0.57b
9	7.74 ± 0.11a	6.60 ± 0.04b	4.75 ± 0.08c	7.61 ± 0.05a	6.61 ± 0.05b	4.96 ± 0.20c	3.88 ± 0.02a	3.11 ± 0.04b	2.01 ± 0.07c	2.87 ± 0.10a	3.22 ± 0.02b	3.11 ± 0.08b
10	6.90 ± 0.22a	7.76 ± 0.32b	6.78 ± 0.10a	7.22 ± 0.02a	6.79 ± 1.24a	5.96 ± 0.10ab	5.32 ± 0.27a	5.00 ± 0.02ab	4.51 ± 0.00c	2.83 ± 0.02a	3.04 ± 0.07b	3.57 ± 0.00c
11		7.86 ± 0.02a	7.52 ± 0.05b		7.34 ± 0.25a	6.92 ± 0.48a		7.66 ± 0.10a	5.15 ± 0.08b		2.13 ± 0.11a	2.85 ± 0.04b
12		7.10 ± 0.08a	6.85 ± 0.01b		6.73 ± 0.17a	6.53 ± 0.39a		6.11 ± 0.02a	6.66 ± 0.11b		2.19 ± 0.05a	2.37 ± 0.02b
13		6.78 ± 0.14a	6.45 ± 0.20a		7.11 ± 0.05a	6.01 ± 0.30b		6.94 ± 0.32a	6.51 ± 0.12a		2.47 ± 0.08a	2.22 ± 0.05b

Table S11. Concentration of several oxidation products, determined by ¹H NMR and expressed as mmol/mol TG, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.1% (SF01_70) and 0.5% (SF05_70) subjected to accelerated storage conditions. The data correspond to those in Figure 8e-h. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among samples.

Time (days)	<i>E,E-2,4-alkadienals</i>			<i>4,5-epoxy-E-2-alkenals</i>			<i>4-oxo-2-alkenals</i>			<i>E,Z-2,4-alkadienals</i>		
	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70	SF0_70	SF01_70	SF05_70
0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0.07 ± 0.00a	0.02 ± 0.00b	0.06 ± 0.00a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.09 ± 0.00b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.07 ± 0.00a	0.02 ± 0.00b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.04 ± 0.00a	0.04 ± 0.00a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	0.03 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00b	0.10 ± 0.00c	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	0.60 ± 0.00a	0.24 ± 0.00b	0.06 ± 0.00c	0.25 ± 0.00	-	-	0.02 ± 0.00	-	-	0.06 ± 0.00	-	-
7	1.22 ± 0.00a	0.69 ± 0.08b	0.59 ± 0.00c	1.03 ± 0.00a	0.32 ± 0.00b	0.33 ± 0.00b	0.17 ± 0.00a	0.03 ± 0.00b	0.04 ± 0.00b	0.08 ± 0.00a	0.05 ± 0.00b	0.08 ± 0.00a
8	2.81 ± 0.10a	2.08 ± 0.02b	1.87 ± 0.00c	2.46 ± 0.08a	1.40 ± 0.00b	0.99 ± 0.01c	0.21 ± 0.03a	0.27 ± 0.03ab	0.18 ± 0.00a	0.26 ± 0.05a	0.18 ± 0.01b	0.27 ± 0.03a
9	2.97 ± 0.08a	2.31 ± 0.00b	2.33 ± 0.02b	2.76 ± 0.03a	1.90 ± 0.00b	1.36 ± 0.02c	0.21 ± 0.00a	0.14 ± 0.00b	0.22 ± 0.00a	0.19 ± 0.01a	0.16 ± 0.00b	0.15 ± 0.00b
10	2.63 ± 0.04a	3.20 ± 0.10b	3.08 ± 0.07b	2.16 ± 0.02a	2.44 ± 0.14ab	1.91 ± 0.00c	0.39 ± 0.02a	0.31 ± 0.02b	0.29 ± 0.05b	-	-	0.19 ± 0.01
11		2.99 ± 0.11a	2.94 ± 0.00a		2.56 ± 0.00a	2.40 ± 0.02b		0.37 ± 0.02a	0.27 ± 0.01b		-	-
12		2.74 ± 0.20a	2.59 ± 0.05a		2.89 ± 0.07a	2.91 ± 0.00a		0.51 ± 0.10a	0.53 ± 0.05a		-	-
13		2.33 ± 0.00a	2.46 ± 0.03b		2.89 ± 0.00a	2.90 ± 0.05a		0.61 ± 0.08a	0.52 ± 0.03a		-	-

Table S12. Abundances of the several tocopherol-derived metabolites, determined by DI-SPME-GC/MS, in sunflower oil, either non-enriched (SF0_70) or enriched with a tocopherol natural extract at 0.5% (SF05_70) subjected to accelerated storage conditions. The data correspond to those in Figure 5c,d. Different letters within each row for each heating time and for each compound indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between samples.

Time (hours)	P		TrMPD		TeMPD		TrMD		TQ23E		7F58DT		5F78DT	
	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70	SF0_70	SF0.5_70
0	10.3 ± 1.1a	47.3 ± 5.0b	-	25.4 ± 1.5	9.6 ± 0.8a	29.9 ± 3.0b	-	-	-	1.7 ± 0.0	-	-	-	-
48	19.7 ± 2.5a	75.0 ± 3.4b	7.4 ± 1.0a	31.4 ± 2.2b	25.5 ± 2.6a	63.9 ± 5.4b	3.5 ± 0.0a	8.6 ± 0.3b	2.1 ± 0.0a	3.1 ± 0.0a	-	0.2 ± 0.0	-	0.7 ± 0.0
96	29.6 ± 0.9a	83.8 ± 4.2b	7.9 ± 0.9a	43.1 ± 5.8b	78.5 ± 6.5a	232.2 ± 22.7b	8.9 ± 0.8a	26.5 ± 2.0b	5.4 ± 0.3a	12.0 ± 0.8b	-	0.5 ± 0.0	-	1.0 ± 0.0
168	22.3 ± 5.0a	71.9 ± 8.7b	44.9 ± 8.3a	65.0 ± 7.3b	206.3 ± 25.3a	397.4 ± 40.2b	18.0 ± 1.7a	42.3 ± 5.4b	8.7 ± 1.6a	22.2 ± 4.7b	-	0.3 ± 0.0	-	0.9 ± 0.0

P: Prist-1-ene; TrMPD: 6,10,14-trimethylpentadecan-2-one; TeMPD: 4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide; TrMD: 3,7,11-trimethyl-3-dodecanol; TQ23E: α -tocopherylquinone-2,3-epoxide; 5F78DT: 5-formyl-7,8-dimethyltolcol; 7F58DT: 7-formyl-5,8-dimethyltolcol.